

1 **Transcriptional noise involving transposase activation.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

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8 We describe here transcriptional noise resulting from compensatory transposase activation following
9 changes in the transcriptome resulting from diverse sources, resembling that which occurs following
10 low-grade oncogene expression.

11 Citations

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